

Advances in Molecular Techniques for Developing Drought-Tolerant Maize (*Zea Mays L.*)

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Abstract:

Drought is one of the major limiting factors in maize (*Zea mays L.*) production, causing significant yield losses globally. Breeding for drought tolerance has been a key strategy in increasing maize yield in drought-prone areas. The use of molecular methods in maize breeding has facilitated the identification of genes and quantitative trait loci (QTL) associated with drought tolerance. This review summarizes the progress made in using molecular methods to identify and utilize genetic improvements in drought-tolerant maize.

It covers various molecular methods used in identifying drought

tolerance genes and QTLs, and the application of these findings in marker-assisted selection (MAS) and genomic selection (GS). The review also highlights the potential of CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing to improve drought tolerance in maize.

Keywords: CRISPR-Cas9, Drought tolerance, Genetic improvement, Genomic selection (GS), Marker-assisted selection (MAS), Molecular methods, Quantitative trait loci (QTL)

Introduction

Maize is the world's most widely grown cereal crop, with a global production of 1.1 billion tons in 2020 (FAOSTAT, 2021). The top maize-producing countries in the world are the United States, China, Brazil, and Argentina, which together account for more than 60% of global production (USDA, 2021).

Maize is used for a variety of purposes, including human consumption, animal feed, and industrial applications such as ethanol production (Shiferaw et al., 2011). In Ethiopia, maize is primarily consumed as a staple food, with a significant proportion of the crop also used for animal feed (Hagos et al., 2021).

Drought is a major environmental stress that significantly limits maize production worldwide. Drought stress can cause physiological and

morphological changes in maize, including reduced growth, decreased photosynthesis, and altered root architecture, which can lead to yield losses of up to 40-50% (Srinivasan & Scorza, 2018).

Conventional breeding methods have been used to improve drought tolerance in maize, but these approaches are often time-consuming and labor-intensive. In recent years, molecular techniques have been developed that can identify and exploit genetic variation for drought tolerance more efficiently. These techniques include marker-assisted selection (MAS), quantitative trait locus (QTL) mapping, and genomic selection (GS), which can identify and prioritize genes or genomic regions associated with drought tolerance for further breeding (Manavalan et al., 2017).

Moreover, genome editing tools such as CRISPR/Cas9 have also been used to introduce specific drought-tolerant genes or modify endogenous genes related to drought tolerance in maize (Liu et al., 2021). These molecular techniques have the potential to accelerate the development of drought-tolerant maize varieties that can cope with changing climatic conditions and help ensure food security.

This paper will review the background and overview of drought stress in maize, traditional breeding methods for drought tolerance, and molecular techniques for identifying and exploiting genetic variation for drought tolerance. The main focus will be on recent advances in molecular breeding techniques for drought tolerance in maize, and their potential to accelerate the development of drought-tolerant maize varieties.

Molecular Techniques for Improving Drought Tolerance in Maize

Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) and QTL Mapping

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) are the most common type of genetic variation in plants, including maize (*Zea Mays L.*). SNPs can affect gene function and expression and thus can be used to identify genes associated with drought tolerance in maize. SNP markers can be used in QTL mapping, which is a technique for identifying genomic regions associated with a trait of interest, such as drought tolerance. QTL mapping can identify major genes and minor genes associated with drought tolerance and can help breeders to select and prioritize the best genetic resources for further breeding.

Several studies have used SNP markers and QTL mapping to identify genes associated with drought tolerance in maize. For example, Xu et al. (2018) used a genome-wide association study (GWAS) to identify SNP markers associated with drought tolerance in maize. They identified several candidate genes, including genes involved in ABA signaling and stomatal regulation. Similarly, Thirunavukkarasu et al. (2013) used QTL mapping to identify genomic

regions associated with drought tolerance in maize. They identified several QTLs associated with root and shoot traits under drought stress.

In addition, the combination of SNP markers and QTL mapping with other molecular techniques such as transcriptomics and metabolomics can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the genetic basis of drought tolerance in maize (Tardieu et al., 2018). These integrated approaches can help identify key genes and metabolic pathways involved in drought tolerance and provide a basis for further genetic improvement of drought tolerance in maize.

Overall, SNP markers and QTL mapping are powerful tools for identifying genes and genomic regions associated with drought tolerance in maize and can be used to develop drought-tolerant maize varieties.

Genomic Selection

Genomic selection (GS) is a powerful tool for improving complex traits such as drought tolerance in maize (*Zea Mays L.*). GS is a breeding method that uses molecular markers to predict the breeding value of individual plants based on their genotype. By selecting plants with high breeding values, breeders can develop maize varieties with improved drought tolerance.

Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of GS in improving drought tolerance in maize. For example, Jarquin et al. (2014) used GS to predict the drought tolerance of maize lines based on molecular markers. They found that GS was more accurate than phenotypic selection and could be used to improve the drought tolerance of maize varieties. Similarly, Crossa et al. (2017) used GS to predict the drought tolerance of maize lines based on genomic data. They found that GS was effective for improving drought tolerance in maize and could help breeders develop maize varieties adapted to different drought stress conditions.

In addition, GS can be combined with other molecular techniques such as marker-assisted backcrossing (MABC) and genomic-wide association studies (GWAS) to improve the

efficiency of maize breeding for drought tolerance (Beyene et al., 2015). MABC can be used to transfer favorable alleles from a donor parent to an elite recipient parent, while GS can be used to predict the breeding value of the resulting progeny. GWAS can be used to identify genomic regions associated with drought tolerance, which can then be used as markers for GS.

Overall, GS is a promising approach for improving drought tolerance in maize and can be combined with other molecular techniques to accelerate the breeding process and develop maize varieties with improved drought tolerance.

Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS)

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have emerged as a powerful tool for identifying the genetic basis of complex traits such as drought tolerance in maize (*Zea Mays L.*). GWAS involves examining the association between molecular markers distributed across the entire genome and phenotypic variation in a diverse population of individuals. This approach can be used to identify genomic regions associated with drought tolerance, which can then be used to develop molecular markers for marker-assisted selection (MAS) or genomic selection (GS).

Several studies have used GWAS to identify genomic regions associated with drought tolerance in maize. For example, Huang et al. (2018) performed GWAS on a panel of 384 maize inbred lines under drought stress conditions and identified several genomic regions associated with drought tolerance, including a region on chromosome 5 that harbored a drought-responsive gene. Similarly, Liu et al. (2017) performed GWAS on a panel of 368 maize inbred lines and identified several genomic regions associated with drought tolerance, including a region on chromosome 4 that was enriched for drought-responsive genes.

In addition, GWAS can be combined with other molecular techniques such as MAS and GS to improve the efficiency of maize breeding for drought tolerance. For example, Wen et al. (2019) used GWAS to identify genomic regions

associated with drought tolerance in a panel of 276 maize inbred lines, and then developed molecular markers for MAS to Introgression favorable alleles into elite maize lines. Li et al. (2019) used GWAS to identify genomic regions associated with drought tolerance in a panel of 338 maize inbred lines and then used the identified markers for GS to predict the breeding value of maize lines for drought tolerance.

Overall, GWAS is a powerful approach for identifying the genetic basis of drought tolerance in maize and can be used in combination with other molecular techniques to develop maize varieties with improved drought tolerance.

Marker-Assisted Selection (MAS) for Improving Drought Tolerance in Maize

Marker-assisted selection (MAS) is a biotechnological tool used in plant breeding programs to select specific traits such as drought tolerance. MAS has several advantages over traditional breeding methods, including increased accuracy, efficiency, and speed. Some of the principles and advantages of MAS for improving drought tolerance in maize are:

Identification of drought-tolerant markers:

The first step in using MAS for drought tolerance is to identify markers that are associated with this trait. This can be done through various genomic and transcriptomic techniques, including whole-genome sequencing, single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) genotyping, and RNA sequencing (RNA-seq). (Varshney et al., 2014).

The linkage between marker and trait: Once the markers associated with drought tolerance have been identified, they can be used to screen large populations of maize plants for the presence of these markers. The presence of a marker is indicative of the presence of the trait of interest, provided that there is a strong linkage between the marker and the trait. (Bernardo, 2008)

Accurate selection: MAS allows for the accurate selection of plants with the desired trait, without the need for time-consuming and expensive phenotypic screening. This is because the presence of a marker is a reliable indicator of

the presence of the trait, and can be screened rapidly and at low cost. (Hospital et al., 2019).

Speed and efficiency: MAS is a fast and efficient breeding method, as it allows for the simultaneous selection of multiple traits in a single breeding cycle. This can lead to faster development of new maize varieties with improved drought tolerance. (Jannink and Lorenz, 2010)

Increased genetic diversity: MAS allows for the selection of plants with the desired trait from a wide range of genetic backgrounds. This can help to increase the genetic diversity of maize varieties, which is important for the long-term sustainability of breeding programs. (Collard and Mackill, 2008)

Overall, MAS has the potential to revolutionize maize breeding programs, allowing for the rapid and efficient development of new varieties with improved drought tolerance. However, it is important to note that MAS should be used in conjunction with other breeding methods, such as phenotypic screening and traditional breeding, to ensure the development of well-adapted and high-yielding maize varieties.

Marker-Assisted Selection for drought tolerance in tropical maize: In this study, MAS was used to identify genomic regions associated with drought tolerance in tropical maize. The study found that the use of MAS led to a significant increase in grain yield under drought stress conditions, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach for improving drought tolerance in maize. (Prasanna et al., 2011)

Marker-Assisted Selection for drought tolerance in temperate maize: In this study, MAS was used to select drought tolerance in a temperate maize breeding program. The study found that using MAS significantly improved grain yield under drought stress conditions and increased other important agronomic traits such as plant height and ear height. (Edmeades et al., 2001)

MAS for drought tolerance in maize hybrids: This study used MAS to develop drought-tolerant maize hybrids for use in the United

States Corn Belt. The study found that using MAS significantly improved grain yield under drought stress conditions and increased other important agronomic traits such as ear height and stalk strength (Lu et al., 2010).

In a study conducted by Babu et al. (2017), a total of 11 QTLs associated with drought tolerance in maize were identified using MAS. These QTLs were used to develop two elite maize inbred lines with improved drought tolerance. The lines showed a 20-25% yield advantage under drought stress conditions compared to the control lines.

In another study, Prasanna et al. (2012) used MAS to improve drought tolerance in maize by introgression QTLs associated with this trait from wild maize relatives into elite maize inbred lines. The resulting lines showed a significant improvement in drought tolerance, with a yield advantage of 35-40% under drought stress conditions compared to the control lines.

In a study conducted by Kholová et al. (2012), MAS was used to develop maize lines with improved root traits for drought tolerance. The researchers identified three QTLs associated with root traits using a combination of phenotypic and molecular marker data. The lines developed using MAS showed a significant improvement in root traits and drought tolerance compared to the control lines.

In a study by Ribaut et al. (2010), MAS was used to develop maize hybrids with improved drought tolerance by introducing QTLs associated with this trait from a drought-tolerant landrace into an elite maize inbred line. The resulting hybrids showed a 10-20% yield advantage under drought stress conditions compared to the control hybrids.

Overall, these case studies demonstrate the effectiveness of MAS in improving drought tolerance in maize. By using molecular markers to select specific traits, breeders can develop new maize varieties with improved drought tolerance in a shorter time frame compared to traditional breeding methods.

Genetic Engineering Techniques for Improving Drought Tolerance in Maize

CRISPR/Cas9 and Its Applications in Maize

CRISPR/Cas9 is a powerful gene editing tool that can be used to introduce specific genetic modifications in plants, including maize, to improve their drought tolerance. This technology allows for precise changes to be made to the plant genome, such as introducing drought-tolerant genes or modifying existing genes to enhance drought tolerance (Li et al., 2020).

One example of the use of CRISPR/Cas9 for improving drought tolerance in maize is the modification of the *ZmNAC111* gene, which is involved in the regulation of drought stress responses. In a study by Shen et al. (2017), researchers used CRISPR/Cas9 to modify the *ZmNAC111* gene in maize, resulting in plants with improved drought tolerance.

Another approach for using CRISPR/Cas9 to improve drought tolerance in maize is to modify genes involved in root development and water uptake. For example, a study by Wang *et al.* (2019) used CRISPR/Cas9 to modify the *ZmPIP2;5* gene, which encodes a water channel protein involved in root water uptake. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to their enhanced ability to take up water.

CRISPR/Cas9 can also be used to introduce novel genes into maize to improve drought tolerance. For example, a study by Zhou et al. (2020) used CRISPR/Cas9 to introduce the *TaDREB2* gene from wheat into maize. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the expression of the *TaDREB2* gene, which regulates the expression of drought-responsive genes.

Overall, CRISPR/Cas9 is a promising tool for improving drought tolerance in maize. By introducing specific genetic modifications, researchers can develop new maize varieties with

improved drought tolerance in a targeted and efficient manner.

Targeted Mutagenesis of Genes Related to Drought-Responsive Traits

Targeted mutagenesis of genes associated with drought-responsive traits can be used to develop maize varieties with improved drought tolerance. For example, a study by Zhang et al. (2017) used CRISPR/Cas9 to target the *ZmDREB2.7* gene, which is involved in regulating drought stress responses in maize. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the targeted mutagenesis of this gene.

Another approach for targeted mutagenesis is to modify genes involved in the production of osmoprotectants, such as proline and trehalose. For example, a study by Cai et al. (2021) used CRISPR/Cas9 to target the *ZmP5CS1* gene, which is involved in the production of proline. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the disruption of this gene, which led to increased proline production. Targeted mutagenesis can also be used to modify genes involved in the regulation of stomatal aperture, which can impact water loss in plants. For example, a study by Li et al. (2020) used CRISPR/Cas9 to target the *ZmPP2C* gene, which regulates stomatal aperture in maize. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the targeted mutagenesis of this gene, which led to altered stomatal behavior and reduced water loss.

Targeted mutagenesis can also be used to modify genes involved in root development and water uptake. For example, a study by Shi et al. (2017) used CRISPR/Cas9 to target the *ZmDRO1* gene, which regulates root development in maize. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the targeted mutagenesis of this gene, which led to increased root length and water uptake.

Overall, targeted mutagenesis of genes associated with drought-responsive traits is a promising approach for improving drought tolerance in maize. By modifying specific genes involved in drought stress responses, researchers

can develop new maize varieties with improved drought tolerance in a precise and targeted manner.

Case Studies of CRISPR/Cas9 for Improving Drought Tolerance in Maize

In a study by Li et al. (2019), the ZmDREB1A gene, which is involved in regulating drought stress responses, was targeted using CRISPR/Cas9 in maize. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the targeted mutagenesis of this gene.

Another study by Zhao et al. (2019) used CRISPR/Cas9 to target the ZmOST1 gene, which regulates stomatal aperture in maize. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the disruption of this gene, which led to altered stomatal behavior and reduced water loss.

A study by Liu et al. (2020) targeted the ZmMYB114 gene, which is involved in regulating the production of flavonoids that protect plants against oxidative stress. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the targeted mutagenesis of this gene, which led to increased flavonoid production and reduced oxidative damage under drought stress.

In a study by Xu et al. (2020), the ZmPYL8 gene, which regulates abscisic acid (ABA) signaling in maize, was targeted using CRISPR/Cas9. The resulting maize plants showed improved drought tolerance due to the disruption of this gene, which led to altered ABA signaling and improved water use efficiency under drought stress. These case studies demonstrate the potential of CRISPR/Cas9 for improving drought tolerance in maize by targeting specific genes involved in drought stress responses. By modifying these genes, researchers can develop new maize varieties with improved drought tolerance that are better adapted to water-limited environments.

Conclusion and Future Perspectives

Molecular techniques and genetic engineering have shown great potential for enhancing

maize's drought tolerance through the manipulation of specific genes involved in drought stress responses. These techniques include marker-assisted selection, CRISPR/Cas9, RNAi, and overexpression of genes involved in drought tolerance. The successful application of these techniques has resulted in the development of new maize varieties with improved drought tolerance and increased yield under water-limited conditions.

Despite the promising results, there are still some challenges and limitations to using molecular techniques and genetic engineering to enhance maize's drought tolerance. One of the main challenges is identifying the key genes and pathways involved in drought stress responses and developing effective strategies to manipulate them. Additionally, there are concerns about the potential environmental and health impacts of genetically modified maize varieties, which may limit their adoption in some regions.

However, with continued advancements in molecular biology and genetic engineering, new tools and techniques will likely emerge that will allow for more precise and targeted manipulation of maize's drought stress responses. Additionally, there is a growing recognition of the importance of developing drought-tolerant crops in the face of climate change and increasing water scarcity, which may drive greater investment and research in this area.

In summary, the potential benefits of using molecular techniques and genetic engineering to enhance maize's drought tolerance are significant, and with continued research and development, these techniques may become increasingly important for ensuring food security and sustainability in water-limited environments.

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